

MARKET INTEGRATION OF MAJOR PULSES IN AMRAVATIDISTRICT OF MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract

India is the world's leading producer, consumer, and importer of pulses, accounting for 25% of worldwide output, 27% of global consumption, and 14% of global imports, respectively. The present study was based on secondary time series data compiled from the monthly arrivals and prices of Pigeon pea and Gram for the periods 2001-2002 to 2020 – 2021. For this purpose, we select two APMCs i.e., Amravati and Daryapur. Data was analyzed by using simple tabular analysis technique. The result found that there was very high degree of association of Pigeon pea prices between these two markets which is 0.627 and it was very highly significant at one per cent level of significance. The Amravati and Daryapur markets are nearby so that may be the reason of high degree of association between these two markets. Therefore, the price signal easily transferred between Amravati and Daryapur. In case of Gram, there was very high degree of association of prices between these two markets which was 0.997 and it was very highly significant at one per cent level of significance. The Amravati and Daryapur markets are nearby so that may be the reason of high degree of association between these two markets. Therefore, the price signal easily transferred between Amravati and Daryapur.

Keywords: Market integration, Pearson correlation, Prices, Pigeon pea and Gram,

Introduction

Pulses are most important crop which grown all over India. The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) classifies pulses into 11 different categories: dry beans, dry broad beans, dry peas, chickpeas, cow peas, pigeon peas, lentils, Bambara beans, vetches, lupins, and pulses in 171 countries throughout the world plant pulses, which have an important role in diet of humans. In India, split pulses are prepared and served as food, known as "Dal". The demand of a man on the street is more for Dal- Roti and Dal-Chawal, and pulses are a nutrient rich food. As the primary source of dietary protein, pulses constitute a staple food for millions of people. They are frequently referred to as "Poor man's meat" and "rich man's vegetable" because they are good sources of plant-based protein and micronutrients, low in fat, and high in dietary fibre. The amount of protein in pulses is 20–25 percent, which is double that of wheat and more than double that of rice. Pulses maintenance the soil fertility by supplying roughly 30 to 40 kg of nitrogen per hectare through biological fixation during crop rotation. In India pulses are grown in two seasons, *kharif* or rainy season and in *rabi* or winter season. There are different types of pulses are grown in all over India, which includes chickpea, pigeon pea, black gram, green gram, lentil, lablab bean, moth bean, cowpea, horse gram and broad bean. Chickpea, pigeon pea, black gram, green gram, lentil and other pulses are contributing 41.20 percent,

19.11 percent, 13.05 percent, 9.62 percent and 17.03 percent to the total production of pulses in the country respectively. India's total pulse production is about 29 percent of total World area and 19 percent of World production respectively.

India is the world's leading producer, consumer, and importer of pulses, accounting for 25% of worldwide output, 27% of global consumption, and 14% of global imports, respectively. The top five States for producing pulses are Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Rajasthan, Uttar Pradesh, and Karnataka. India is the leading producer of pulses in the World. India is also the largest consumer about 27 percent global production in India, which is first rank in production of pulses, which contributes 34-35 percent of total area and 25-27 percent global production. In the World the production of pulses was 89.9 million metric tonnes during 2020-21. China, Australia and South Africa in descending order are also major pulses producing countries after India. (Source- Statista). There is considerable increase in area, production and productivity of pulses crops in India from the year 2015-16 to 2020-21. The area of pulses in 2020-21 was 28.78 Mha and production was 25.75 Mt. The productivity of pulses crops in the year 2020-21 was 885 Kg/ha. (Source- www.indiaagristat.com). The

scenario of rabi and kharif pulses production of Indian state like Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Maharashtra were 5.30 Mt and it accounts for 20.60 percent, 4.31 Mt and it accounts for 16.75 percent and 4.30 Mt and it accounts for 16.71 percent share of total pulses production respectively in India during 2021-22

(Source- Directorate of Economics & Statistics, Department of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare).

Pigeon pea (*cajanus cajan*) is the second most important pulse crop grown all over India. It accounts for about 18 percent total pulses production in India. The common name of pigeon pea in various areas is "tur or tuwar, arhar, red gram". Pigeon pea is recognized as 'tur' in most of the regions of Maharashtra. Pigeon pea cultivated in *kharif* season as an intercrop as well as mixed crop. Which is required moderate hot climate due to these they are cultivated in *kharif* season. Gram (*Cicer arietinum*) is the first largest pulse crop grown all over India. In Maharashtra Gram recognized as 'Chana' and which accounts for about 40 percent of total pulses production in India. The origin of Gram is South West Asia (Afghanistan). It was introduced in 2300 BC. Gram crop is the leading pulse crop in area and production. Which crop is grown mostly in the *rabi* season because this crop requires moderate cold climate for its cultivation. Gram is used for making dal, besan, bhajiyas, besan laddu & barfi, papadi, etc.

The primary purpose of this investigation study is to develop a clear understanding market integration of the major pulses in the Agriculture Produce Market Committee (APMC), Amravati district of Maharashtra, which can be shared with the relevant line departments, institutions, agencies, and NGOs to understand the current knowledge and adoption pattern of marketing, help the farmer locate their produce, and help them decide when to sell in order to get the best price. By being aware of acceptable agricultural practices and implementing them, they will be able to create priorities for carrying out activities and actions to boost the farmer's revenue and profitability. The present investigation is restricted to market integration of Pulses crops especially Gram and Pigeon Pea production in Amravati district. For this purpose, we taken one objective i.e., market integration of major pulses in Amravati district of Maharashtra.

Materials and Methods

The present study was based on secondary time series data compiled from the monthly arrivals and prices of Pigeon pea and Gram. In Amravati district there are twelve main APMCs Amravati, Achalpur, Anjangaon Surji, Chandur Bajar, Chandur Railway, Dhamangao Railway, Daryapur, Dharni, Morshi, Nandgaon Khandeshwar, Teosa & Warud in which Amravati and Daryapur APMC has highest arrivals and

prices of pulses as compared to other APMCs so that these two was selected for the research period. Data were collected from the record of the selected market committee i.e., Amravati and Daryapur and Maharashtra State Agriculture Marketing Board (MSAMB), Pune. The monthly arrivals and prices data pertend for the periods 2001-2002 to 2020 – 2021 was collected for this study.

Analytical tools and Technique

Data will be analysed by using simple tabular analytical tools such as mean, frequencies, ratios, percentages etc. Apart from this, functional analysis will also be used for computation such as market integration, bivariate analysis. Market integration was worked out by estimating

Results and Discussion

Table 1: Market Integration of Pigeon pea in Amravati and Daryapur Market:

		Amravati	Daryapur
Amravati	Pearson Correlation	1	.627**
	Sig. (2 – tailed)		0.003
	N	20	20
	Pearson Correlation	.627**	1
	Sig. (2 – tailed)	0.003	
	N	20	20

** Correlation is significant at the 1 per cent level (2- tailed)

Table 1 shows the Pearson correlation analysis of Pigeon pea prices in Amravati and Daryapur market. The result found that there was very high degree of association of prices between these two markets which is 0.627 and it was very highly significant at one per cent level of significance. The Amravati and Daryapur markets are nearby so that may be the reason of high degree of association between these two markets. Therefore, the price signal easily transferred between Amravati

Table 2: Market Integration of Gram in Amravati and Daryapur Market:

		Amravati	Daryapur
Amravati	Pearson Correlation	1	.997**
	Sig. (2 – tailed)		0.000
	N	20	20
Daryapur	Pearson Correlation	.997**	1
	Sig. (2 – tailed)	0.000	
	N	20	20

** Correlation is significant at the 1 per cent level (2- tailed)

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlation analysis of Gram prices in Amravati and Daryapur market. The result found that there was very high degree of association of prices between these two markets which was 0.997 and it was very highly significant at one per cent level of significance. The Amravati and Daryapur markets are nearby so that may be the reason of high degree of association between these two markets. Therefore, the price signal easily transferred between Amravati and Daryapur. Similarly, Tingre *et al.* (2021) noted that maize prices series of all selected markets were stationary at level. The selected markets showed long run equilibrium relationship and cointegration between them.

Conclusion

Result concluded that, in Pigeon pea the Amravati and Daryapur shows high degree of association between them may be due to they are nearby markets. Therefore, the price signal is easily transferred between Amravati and Daryapur market. In case of Gram, there is high degree of association of prices of Gram in these two markets and it is found significant at one percent level of significance. The Amravati and Daryapur markets are nearby so it may be the reason behind high degree of association between these two markets. Therefore, the price signal easily transferred between Amravati and Daryapur.

bivariate correlation coefficient between price changes in different selected market. [Acharya and Agarwal (1994)]

$$r = \frac{\sum(P_{11} - P_1)(P_{21} - P_2)}{\sqrt{\sum(P_{11} - P_1)^2 \sum(P_{21} - P_2)^2}}$$

r = Simple correlation coefficient

P₁₁ = Price of the commodity in first market P₂₁ = Price of the commodity in second market P₁ = Mean of prices in first market

P₂ = Mean of the prices in second market

and Daryapur.

Nayak *et al.* (2020) analysed market integration across six major wholesale markets for Groundnut, Sunflower and Soybean and which confirmed that some markets are influencing each other in a unidirectional way and found that the regional markets for selected pulses are strongly co-integrated.

Policy Implications

The record of quantity of arrivals should be checked regularly. Government should appoint a committee for that so that everything should be maintained regularly. Government should ensure that there must be availability of reliable and consistent data about prices and arrivals on daily basis in different markets. The flow of market information must be speed up as the market information plays an important role in linking the distance markets. It will help in improving the marketing efficiency. There must be strengthening of good information network system for the flow of price information.

There must be improvement in the storage facilities through improvement in warehouse structure, storage chambers in order to improve the retention capacity of the farmers. It will also help to reduce the post-harvest losses.

The researchers and policy makers have to pay more attention to develop location specific cultural practice to increase and sustain pulses production and yield in the nation. Easy transportation facilities should be made available to every part of nation so that producers can get better price benefits from such markets.

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